

Order Restricted Cluster Randomized Block Design

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Abstract

This research introduces a novel two-stage cluster randomized design, the order restricted cluster randomized block design (ORCRBD). The ORCRBD builds upon the cluster randomized block design by incorporating a second layer of blocking, achieved through ranking cluster units that are randomly sampled from the population. This approach creates a two-way layout, with blocks and ranking groups, and employs restricted randomization to enhance the accuracy of treatment contrast estimation. We calculate the expected mean square for each source of variation in the ORCRBD under a suitable linear model, develop an approximate F -test for the treatment effect, assess ranking quality, calculate optimal sample sizes for a given cost model, formulate multiple comparison procedures, and apply the design to an educational setting.

Key Words: order restricted randomization, ranked set sampling, intracluster correlation coefficient, Latin square, optimal design

1. Background Information

The cluster randomized design (CRD) is a unique experimental approach extensively employed across fields such as education, social sciences, and medicine to evaluate the impact of specific methodologies or policies on groups rather than individuals. This design has proven instrumental in the assessment of various intervention programs, including health treatments (Menya et al., 2015; Cundill et al., 2015), vaccination initiatives (Roca et al., 2011), and educational strategies (Wing et al., 2015; Tol et al., 2014). Distinguishing itself from a conventional randomized experiment, a CRD allocates treatments to predefined clusters (e.g., schools, neighborhoods, hospitals) rather than individual subjects within the population, thereby addressing the collective effect of the intervention (Moberg and Kramer, 2015).

One of the key advantages of CRDs lies in their efficacy in mitigating the risk of contamination, a common challenge in studies where interventions are susceptible to being influenced by interactions among participants from different treatment groups. This is a common issue in clinical and educational research settings, as participants can inadvertently affect the outcomes of others, thereby muddying the results. By allocating the intervention at the cluster level, CRDs reduce this risk, maintaining the integrity of the data collection process.

Subjects within the same cluster unit of a cluster randomized design typically exhibit greater homogeneity compared to subjects in different cluster units. This homogeneity is often quantified using the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC). A CRD with a large ICC tends to have lower statistical power than a completely randomized design with the same number of subjects (Kramer et al., 2009). Researchers have explored methods to mitigate the impact of a large ICC in CRDs. For example, Raudenbush (1997) found

that a covariance analysis with a within- or between-cluster covariate improves statistical precision.

CRDs involve two sample sizes: the number of cluster units and the number of within-cluster units. The optimal selection of these sample sizes can enhance the efficiency of a CRD for a pre-specified budget. This optimization process depends on various factors, including the sampling cost of cluster units, the sampling cost of within-cluster units, the *ICC*, and the overall structure of the experimental design. For an in-depth exploration of the design and analysis of CRDs, we refer the readers to several key papers in the field: Murray et al. (2004); Turner et al. (2017a); Turner et al. (2017b); Murray et al. (2020); Murray (2022); and Hemming and Taljaard (2023).

In a CRD, much of the variation arises from differences among cluster units. A successful CRD strategy should, therefore, aim to minimize the impact of cluster level variation. One effective approach is to incorporate a well-defined covariate in the analysis, as suggested by Raudenbush (1997). This method involves fitting a covariance model post-experimentally, but it assumes a strong linear relationship between the response and covariate. For many studies, this assumption may be too strong. An alternative approach that does not rely on this assumption is ranking units prior to treatment allocation. Wang et al. (2016) incorporated this idea in a two-level hierarchical linear model for a CRD, leveraging ranked set sampling (RSS) at the cluster or subsampling level, or both. Wang et al. (2020) also incorporated RSS into a CRD when estimating the treatment effect for binary outcomes. For a detailed review of ranked set sampling, interested readers are encouraged to consult Wolfe (2012), Bouza-Herrera and Al-Omari (2018), and the references therein. Ozturk et al. (2023b) also investigated RSS-structured CRDs, but they took a different approach from Wang et al. (2016). Ozturk et al. (2023b) focused on the design aspect, treating ranking groups as a blocking factor. They introduced the cluster randomized ranked design (CRRD), which allows for more than two treatment levels.

While RSS offers numerous advantages, such as creating homogeneous ranking groups, it does involve discarding units. For instance, in a set of size H , RSS retains only one unit and discards the other $H - 1$ units after ranking. This can be particularly significant when there are limited units available for sampling or when sampling costs are high. To mitigate this issue, in a series of papers, Ozturk and MacEachern (2004, 2007, 2013) introduced order restricted randomization (ORR). Ozturk et al. (2023a) incorporated an ORR design with a Latin square structure.

In this manuscript, we propose a novel design, the order restricted cluster randomized block design (ORCRBD), which offers improved efficiency compared to existing CRDs. The construction of the ORCRBD is motivated using a cluster population of schools. The ORCRBD combines ORR at the cluster level with either RSS or simple random sampling (SRS) at the subsampling level. This design resembles a traditional CRD but includes two blocking factors. One blocking factor arises from ranking sets of cluster units (schools), while the other can be any factor that divides the cluster population into homogeneous groups. For example, if schools are the cluster units, geographic region, size, or type of school could serve as this other blocking factor.

More precisely, the ORCRBD hinges on the assumption that the school population can be separated into H_1 distinct groups (blocks). Each block in the design consists of m sets of H_1 schools which are obtained as follows: from block 1, H_1 schools are randomly selected and, using pre-experimental information (e.g., school income level or past assessment scores), ranked from smallest to largest. These schools make up the first set in block 1. An additional H_1 schools are then randomly selected from the same block and also ranked from smallest to largest using pre-experimental information. These schools comprise the second set in block 1. This process is continued until there are m sets of ranked schools in

block 1. The same process is used in blocks $2, \dots, H_1$. This results in $H_1 m$ sets, each of which contains H_1 ranked schools, for a total of $H_1^2 m$ schools in the design. The ordered schools in the same set are correlated; however, schools in different sets are independent.

Schools are then organized into a row-column structure. Rows are indexed by block and set, but columns are indexed by rank only. The block and rank indices define H_1^2 cells. Each cell contains m schools. The H_1 treatments are randomly assigned to the H_1^2 cells with the following restriction: each treatment appears only once within each block and ranking group.

We illustrate one possible treatment allocation scheme of the ORCRBD in Table 1. In this table, cu_{ikhr} represents the cluster unit (school) in set r of block i that is assigned rank k and treatment h . The notation T_h is used to represent treatment h . The cluster units in block i and ranking group k make up cell (i, k) of the design. Since treatments are allocated to cells, all cluster units (schools) in the same cell receive the same treatment.

Table 1: ORCRBD with $H_1 = 3$ and m cluster units in each cell

Block (i)	Set (r)	Cluster Rank (k)		
		1	2	3
1	1	$T_1 : cu_{1111}$	$T_2 : cu_{1221}$	$T_3 : cu_{1331}$
	2	$T_1 : cu_{1112}$	$T_2 : cu_{1222}$	$T_3 : cu_{1332}$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
	m	$T_1 : cu_{111m}$	$T_2 : cu_{122m}$	$T_3 : cu_{133m}$
2	1	$T_2 : cu_{2121}$	$T_3 : cu_{2231}$	$T_1 : cu_{2311}$
	2	$T_2 : cu_{2122}$	$T_3 : cu_{2232}$	$T_1 : cu_{2312}$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
	m	$T_2 : cu_{212m}$	$T_3 : cu_{223m}$	$T_1 : cu_{231m}$
3	1	$T_3 : cu_{3131}$	$T_1 : cu_{3211}$	$T_2 : cu_{3321}$
	2	$T_3 : cu_{3132}$	$T_1 : cu_{3212}$	$T_2 : cu_{3322}$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
	m	$T_3 : cu_{313m}$	$T_1 : cu_{321m}$	$T_2 : cu_{332m}$

We note that cluster units contain a population of individuals. For example, within schools, the population of interest might be teachers or students. In an experiment, however, it is often not feasible or economical to measure a response for all of these individuals. Therefore, in the ORCRBD, we use subsampling to select p subjects from each cluster unit. These p subjects can be selected via SRS or RSS.

We next describe the process of obtaining a ranked set sample of p subjects in one school, cu_{ikhr} , of an ORCRBD. Initially, we determine a set size H_2 and cycle size d_2 such that $p = H_2 d_2$. It is assumed that p is much smaller than the size of the population. Subsequently, we randomly select $p H_2$ subjects from school cu_{ikhr} and divide them into p sets, each containing H_2 subjects. These subjects are then ranked within each set from smallest to largest, utilizing a method that does not require full measurement, such as an auxiliary variable (e.g., past exam scores) or expert opinion. Following this, we retain the subjects ranked as 1 from the first d_2 sets, the subjects ranked as 2 from the next d_2 sets, and so forth, until retaining the subjects ranked as H_2 from the last d_2 sets. We return the other subjects to the population without measurement. Table 2 illustrates observational units obtained using SRS and RSS in one cell of an ORCRBD.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides general models for the ORCRBD under a consistent ranking scheme and discusses one-parameter ranking models for cluster (stage 1) and within-cluster level (stage 2) sampling. Section 3 presents analysis of variance (ANOVA) tables with expected mean square (EMS) expressions, which are used to derive an approximate F -test for the treatment effect. Section 4 provides optimal sample sizes for a given budget. Section 5 discusses the estimation of treatment contrasts.

cell (i, k) ; and $\epsilon_{t(ikr)}$ is the error term for subject t within cluster r of cell (i, k) . The factors A , B , and C are fixed effects that satisfy sum-to-zero constraints: $\sum_{i=1}^{H_1} \alpha_i = 0$, $\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h = 0$, and $\sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^* = 0$. Factor $D(A)$, the cluster error, and the individual error are assumed to be random. The set effect, $d_{r(i)}$, is assumed to have a standard normal distribution. The cluster error, $c_{r(ik)}^*$, is the k^{th} judgment order statistic (with shifted mean 0) in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution; the mean is shifted to ϕ_k^* . The individual error term, $\epsilon_{t(ikr)}$, is assumed to follow a standard normal distribution. We assume mutual independence among $d_{r(i)}$, $c_{r(ik)}^*$, and $\epsilon_{t(ikr)}$. The judgment order statistics are derived by ranking cluster units within a set of size H_1 . While the ranking process may not be flawless, in the case of perfect ranking, the judgment order statistics align with the order statistics of a sample of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution.

For the ORCRBD with RSS at the subsampling level, we propose the following model:

$$Y_{ikhrvs} = \mu + \alpha_i + \gamma\phi_k^* + \beta_h + \tau d_{r(i)} + \gamma c_{r(ik)}^* + \sigma\omega_v^* + \sigma\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*, \quad i, k, h = 1, \dots, H_1; \\ r = 1, \dots, m; v = 1, \dots, H_2; s = 1, \dots, d_2; p = H_2 d_2; h = b(i, k). \quad (3)$$

In this model, ω_v^* is the v^{th} subsampling ranking group effect (factor S); $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*$ is the error term for the subject with subsampling rank v in subsampling cycle s of cluster r in cell (i, k) ; and the remaining terms are defined the same as they were for model (2). Factor S is a fixed effect satisfying the sum-to-zero constraint, $\sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^* = 0$. The individual error, $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*$, is the v^{th} judgment order statistic (with shifted mean 0) in a set of size H_2 from a standard normal distribution; the mean is shifted to ω_v^* . We assume mutual independence among $d_{r(i)}$, $c_{r(ik)}^*$, and $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*$.

The strength of an ORCRBD lies in its capacity to create distinct ranking blocks at both the cluster and subsampling levels. While the ranking process does not need to be perfect, it must meet certain consistency criteria to yield unbiased estimators. The cluster level ranking mechanism is consistent if the following condition is satisfied:

$$F(y) = \frac{1}{H_1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} F_k^*(y). \quad (4)$$

In this notation, $F(y)$ is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a standard normal random variable, and $F_k^*(y)$ is the CDF of the k^{th} judgment order statistic in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution. This consistency condition holds if the same ranking procedure is used in every set and a unique rank is assigned to every unit in a set (Presnell and Bohn, 1999). We note that the form of $F_k^*(y)$ in equation (4) is generally unknown; it depends on the ranking mechanism. These ideas apply to the subsampling level ranking mechanism as well, with appropriate adjustments in notation.

The quality of the ranking mechanism involves a level of uncertainty, which can be captured through various modeling approaches. For example, Dell and Clutter (1972) developed an additive model of perceptual error. Bohn and Wolfe (1994) proposed the expected spacings model, which hinges on the idea that the CDFs of judgment order statistics can be expressed as a weighted sum of CDFs of order statistics; Frey (2007) generalized this work by subsampling order statistics from the Bohn-Wolfe model. Fligner and MacEachern (2006) introduced a class of ranking models based on perceptions of within-set units using the Monotone Likelihood Ratio principle. In this paper, we use one-parameter ranking models to construct explicit expressions for the distributions of judgment order statistics in models (2) and (3).

We assume there exists an auxiliary variable, W , that can be used to rank cluster units prior to treatment allocation. This auxiliary variable is assumed to be correlated with the

unordered cluster errors. We then model the judgment ranked cluster error term $c_{r(ik)}^*$, with shifted mean 0, for each cluster unit as

$$c_{r(ik)}^*(\rho_1) = \sqrt{1 - \rho_1^2} u_{r(ik)} + \rho_1 w_{r(ik)}^+ - \rho_1 \phi_k. \quad (5)$$

In this model, $\rho_1 = \text{corr}(c_{r(ik)}, w_{r(ik)})$, where $c_{r(ik)}$ is the unordered cluster error term and $w_{r(ik)}$ is the corresponding W value; $u_{r(ik)} \stackrel{\text{ind}}{\sim} N(0, 1)$; $w_{r(ik)}^+$ is the k^{th} order statistic in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution; and $\phi_k = E(w_{r(ik)}^+)$. The ρ_1 parameter controls ranking quality: smaller values of ρ_1 make it harder to obtain an accurate ranking. For instance, if $\rho_1 = 0$, rankings are completely at random and $c_{r(ik)}^*(\rho_1)$ reduces to a standard normal random variable. However, if $\rho_1 = 1$, ranking with respect to $w_{r(ik)}^+$ is perfect and $c_{r(ik)}^*(\rho_1)$ reduces to the k^{th} mean-corrected order statistic in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution. Values of ρ_1 between 0 and 1 represent various other ranking qualities.

Under model (5), we rewrite model (2) as

$$Y_{ikhrt} = \mu + \alpha_i + \rho_1 \gamma \phi_k + \beta_h + \tau d_{r(i)} + \gamma c_{r(ik)}^*(\rho_1) + \sigma \epsilon_{t(ikr)}, \\ i, k, h = 1, \dots, H_1; r = 1, \dots, m; t = 1, \dots, p; h = b(i, k). \quad (6)$$

A similar ranking model can be considered for RSS at the subsampling level. In this case, we assume there exists another auxiliary variable, Z , that can be used for ranking within-cluster units. We assume Z is correlated with the unordered subsampling errors. We model the judgment ranked subsampling error term, with shifted mean 0, for each Y_{ikhrvs} as

$$\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*(\rho_2) = \sqrt{1 - \rho_2^2} u_{sv(ikr)} + \rho_2 z_{sv(ikr)}^+ - \rho_2 \omega_v. \quad (7)$$

In this model, $\rho_2 = \text{corr}(\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}, z_{sv(ikr)})$, where $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}$ is the unordered subsampling error term and $z_{sv(ikr)}$ is the corresponding Z value; $u_{sv(ikr)} \stackrel{\text{ind}}{\sim} N(0, 1)$; $z_{sv(ikr)}^+$ is the v^{th} order statistic in a set of size H_2 from a standard normal distribution; and $\omega_v = E(z_{sv(ikr)}^+)$.

Using models (5) and (7), we rewrite model (3) as

$$Y_{ikhrvs} = \mu + \alpha_i + \rho_1 \gamma \phi_k + \beta_h + \tau d_{r(i)} + \gamma c_{r(ik)}^*(\rho_1) + \rho_2 \sigma \omega_v + \sigma \epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*(\rho_2), \\ i, k, h = 1, \dots, H_1; r = 1, \dots, m; v = 1, \dots, H_2; s = 1, \dots, d_2; p = H_2 d_2; h = b(i, k). \quad (8)$$

3. Statistical Inference for Treatment Effect and Parameter Estimation

Expected mean squares (EMS) for models (1), (6), and (8) are given in Tables 3, 4, and 5, respectively.

The EMS expressions in Tables 4 and 5 suggest an approximate testing procedure for the treatment effect. A test for the treatment effect rejects the null hypothesis of no treatment effect for large values of the F -statistic,

$$F_B = \frac{MSB}{MSCE},$$

where MSB is the mean squared treatment and $MSCE$ is the mean squared cluster error.

The null distribution of F_B is an exact F -distribution only if all rankings are performed completely at random. For the ORCRBD with SRS at the subsampling level, this means $\rho_1 = 0$; for the ORCRBD with RSS at the subsampling level, this means $\rho_1 = 0$ and

Table 3: EMS expressions for model (1)

Source	df	EMS
A	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{H_1} \alpha_i^2$
B	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2$
Cluster Effect (CE)	$H_1^2 m - 2H_1 + 1$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2$
Residual Error (E)	$H_1^2 m(p - 1)$	σ^2

Table 4: EMS expressions for model (6)

Source	df	EMS
A	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 + H_1 p\tau^2 + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{H_1} \alpha_i^2$
B	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right) + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2$
C	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 \left\{1 - \frac{\rho_1^2(1 - H_1 m)}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right\}$
D(A)	$H_1(m - 1)$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 + H_1 p\tau^2$
Cluster Error (CE)	$(H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$	$\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)$
Residual Error (E)	$H_1^2 m(p - 1)$	σ^2

$\rho_2 = 0$. A departure from random rankings leads to non-normal error terms in the form of mean-corrected judgment order statistics, in which case the null distribution of F_B can be approximated by a central F -distribution. The test rejects the null hypothesis of no treatment effect at a significance level, α , if F_B is greater than the critical value, $F_{df_1, df_2, \alpha}$, where $F_{df_1, df_2, \alpha}$ is the upper α^{th} quantile of the central F -distribution with $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$.

We performed a simulation study of size 10,000 under model (8) to explore Type I error rates for this testing procedure. The data were generated assuming the overall mean $\mu = 0$, with no treatment or block effect. In this simulation study, we let $\rho_1 = 0, 1$ and $\rho_2 = 0, 1$. For each combination of ρ_1 and ρ_2 , we specified $H_1 = 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10$; $H_2 = 3, 5$; $d_2 = 2$; $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.01, 0.5$. For the ORCRBD, ICC is expressed mathematically as $ICC = \gamma^2 / (\sigma^2 + \gamma^2)$, where γ^2 and σ^2 are the between- and within-cluster unit variations, respectively. These ICC values were obtained using the following choices of (γ, σ) : $(1, \sqrt{99})$ and $(1, 1)$. The empirical Type I error rates were calculated as the proportion of F_B values greater than the 95th percentile of a central F_{df_1, df_2} distribution, with $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$. The Type I error rates for this simulation study are in Table 6. The Type I error rates are all very close to 0.05, regardless of ranking qualities.

We constructed 95% confidence intervals for the true Type I error rate, 0.05, using the empirical Type I error rates in Table 6. Approximately 89.58% of these confidence intervals

Table 5: EMS expressions for model (8)

Source	df	EMS
<i>A</i>	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 + H_1 p\tau^2 + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{H_1} \alpha_i^2$
<i>B</i>	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right) + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2$
<i>C</i>	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left\{1 - \frac{\rho_1^2(1-H_1m)}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right\}$
<i>D(A)</i>	$H_1(m - 1)$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 + H_1 p\tau^2$
Cluster Error (<i>CE</i>)	$(H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)$
<i>S</i>	$H_2 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + \frac{H_1^2 m d_2}{H_2 - 1} \rho_2^2 \sigma^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2$
Residual Error (<i>E</i>)	$H_1^2 m(p - 1) - (H_2 - 1)$	σ_S^2

Note: $\sigma_S^2 = \sigma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2}{H_2} \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2\right)$

contained 0.05. The empirical Type I error rates whose corresponding confidence intervals did not contain 0.05 are denoted with a “*” in Table 6.

Table 6: Type I error rates for the (approximate) *F*-test of treatment effect

H_1	m	H_2	d_2	ρ_1	ρ_2	<i>ICC</i> = 0.01		<i>ICC</i> = 0.5		<i>ICC</i> = 0.01		<i>ICC</i> = 0.5	
						Type I error	Type I error	ρ_1	ρ_2	Type I error	Type I error		
3	3	3	2	0	0	0.050	0.048	1	0	0.050	0.047		
3	3	5	2	0	0	0.052	0.051	1	0	0.050	0.046*		
3	5	3	2	0	0	0.050	0.050	1	0	0.052	0.053		
3	5	5	2	0	0	0.047	0.047	1	0	0.054	0.048		
3	10	3	2	0	0	0.051	0.051	1	0	0.051	0.049		
3	10	5	2	0	0	0.049	0.053	1	0	0.049	0.049		
4	3	3	2	0	0	0.055*	0.049	1	0	0.049	0.052		
4	3	5	2	0	0	0.050	0.050	1	0	0.049	0.049		
4	5	3	2	0	0	0.049	0.047	1	0	0.050	0.046		
4	5	5	2	0	0	0.050	0.050	1	0	0.049	0.058*		
4	10	3	2	0	0	0.050	0.050	1	0	0.049	0.051		
4	10	5	2	0	0	0.046*	0.050	1	0	0.049	0.050		
3	3	3	2	0	1	0.047	0.047	1	1	0.051	0.046*		
3	3	5	2	0	1	0.046	0.046	1	1	0.052	0.049		
3	5	3	2	0	1	0.049	0.046*	1	1	0.050	0.048		
3	5	5	2	0	1	0.048	0.051	1	1	0.051	0.045*		
3	10	3	2	0	1	0.050	0.048	1	1	0.050	0.050		
3	10	5	2	0	1	0.047	0.048	1	1	0.049	0.046*		
4	3	3	2	0	1	0.046*	0.051	1	1	0.050	0.049		
4	3	5	2	0	1	0.055*	0.053	1	1	0.050	0.049		
4	5	3	2	0	1	0.049	0.050	1	1	0.049	0.053		
4	5	5	2	0	1	0.050	0.054	1	1	0.051	0.046		
4	10	3	2	0	1	0.051	0.050	1	1	0.051	0.053		
4	10	5	2	0	1	0.048	0.050	1	1	0.051	0.051		

Note: * indicates the corresponding 95% confidence interval did not contain 0.05.

In another simulation study, we created quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plots of F_B against the corresponding central *F*-distribution. The empirical evidence from these simulation studies suggests that the null distribution of F_B can be approximated reasonably well by a central

F -distribution for various correlation structures, sample sizes, and ICC values.

We now compare the efficiency of the ORCRBD with the efficiency of the cluster randomized design (CRD), cluster randomized ranked design (CRRD), and cluster randomized block design (CRBD). For the ORCRBD and CRRD, we assume RSS is used at the sub-sampling level. We calculate relative efficiencies using the noncentrality parameters that correspond to the F -statistics for the treatment effect.

The noncentrality parameter for F_B in the ORCRBD is

$$\lambda_{ORCRBD} = \frac{H_1 m p \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2}{E_{ORCRBD}(MSCE)},$$

where

$$E_{ORCRBD}(MSCE) = \sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right).$$

The noncentrality parameter for the CRD is

$$\lambda_{CRD} = \frac{H_1 m p \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2}{E_{CRD}(MSCE)},$$

where

$$E_{CRD}(MSCE) = \sigma^2 + p\gamma^2.$$

The quantity $E_{CRD}(MSCE)$ is provided in Ozturk et al. (2023b). After the necessary notational adjustments for clarity, the relative efficiency of the ORCRBD with respect to the CRD is given as

$$RE_1 = \frac{\lambda_{ORCRBD}}{\lambda_{CRD}} = \frac{\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2}{\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)} = \frac{1 + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}{H_2}\right) + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2 \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}{H_1 - 1}\right)}.$$

The following relationships hold: $\sigma_S^2 = \sigma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2}{H_2} \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2\right) \leq \sigma^2$ and

$p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right) \leq p\gamma^2$. Therefore, $RE_1 \geq 1$. This is a strict inequality as long as $\rho_1 \neq 0$, $\rho_2 \neq 0$, or both. This suggests that the ORCRBD is at least as efficient as the CRD.

The noncentrality parameter for the CRRD is

$$\lambda_{CRRD} = \frac{H_1 m p \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2}{E_{CRRD}(MSCE)},$$

where

$$E_{CRRD}(MSCE) = \sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right).$$

The quantity $E_{CRRD}(MSCE)$ is provided in Ozturk et al. (2023b). After making the necessary notational adjustments, the relative efficiency of the ORCRBD with respect to the CRRD is given as follows:

$$RE_2 = \frac{\lambda_{ORCRBD}}{\lambda_{CRRD}} = \frac{\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)}{\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)} = \frac{\left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}{H_2}\right) + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2 \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}{H_1}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}{H_2}\right) + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2 \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}{H_1 - 1}\right)}.$$

The only difference between the numerator and denominator of RE_2 is that H_1 in the numerator is replaced by $H_1 - 1$ in the denominator. This difference results from the

correlation structure among cluster units in the ORCRBD. For a fixed H_1 , this correlation structure leads to $RE_2 \geq 1$. This inequality is strict as long as $\rho_1 \neq 0$. Hence, the ORCRBD is at least as efficient as the CRRD.

Finally, the noncentrality parameter for the CRBD is

$$\lambda_{CRBD} = \frac{H_1 m p \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2}{E_{CRBD}(MSCE)},$$

where

$$E_{CRBD}(MSCE) = \sigma^2 + p\gamma^2.$$

Thus, the relative efficiency of the ORCRBD with respect to the CRBD is given as follows:

$$RE_3 = \frac{\lambda_{ORCRBD}}{\lambda_{CRBD}} = \frac{\sigma^2 + p\gamma^2}{\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)} = \frac{1 + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}{H_2}\right) + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2 \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}{H_1 - 1}\right)}.$$

Note that, ignoring the effect of the degrees of freedom on the cluster error, the expression for RE_3 is equivalent to RE_1 . Hence, the explanations provided for RE_1 apply to RE_3 as well, and the ORCRBD is at least as efficient as the CRBD.

We present surface plots for RE_3 in Figure 1. When ICC is set at 0.01, ranking quality at the subsampling level has a bigger impact on the relative efficiency than ranking quality at the cluster level. Specifically, the relative efficiency of the ORCRBD with respect to the CRBD considerably increases as ρ_2 increases, but the relative efficiency is fairly stable for all values of ρ_1 . When ICC is set at 0.5, the opposite occurs: the relative efficiency becomes markedly larger as ρ_1 increases but is fairly stable for all values of ρ_2 . This suggests that ranking quality at the cluster level has a bigger impact on relative efficiency than ranking quality at the subsampling level.

Figure 1: Surface plots for RE_3

We performed another simulation study of size 10,000 to explore the empirical power of the test corresponding to F_B in the ORCRBD. The data in this simulation study were generated under the assumption of overall mean $\mu = 0$ and no block effect. The cluster and

subsampling errors were generated using the one-parameter ranking models, which used two sets of correlation structures:

$$\text{Set 1} : \{\rho_1 = 1, \rho_2 = 0, 0.5, 0.75, 1\} \text{ and}$$

$$\text{Set 2} : \{\rho_2 = 1, \rho_1 = 0, 0.5, 0.75, 1\}.$$

For each correlation structure, we used the following simulation parameters: $H_1 = 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10$; $p = 6$ ($H_2 = 3, d_2 = 2$); $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.01, 0.5$. These ICC values were generated using the following values of (γ, σ) : $(1, \sqrt{99})$ and $(1, 1)$, respectively. The nominal size of the hypothesis test was set to $\alpha = 0.05$.

For each combination of simulation parameters, we calculated the empirical power under the following directional alternative hypotheses:

$$H_a : \left\{ \beta_1 = -\frac{\Delta}{2}, \beta_2 = 0, \dots, \beta_{H_1-1} = 0, \beta_{H_1} = \frac{\Delta}{2} \right\},$$

where $\Delta = \delta \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \sigma^2}$ and $\delta = 0(0.2)1$. The empirical power was calculated as the proportion of F_B values exceeding the 95th percentile of a central F -distribution with numerator and denominator degrees of freedom, $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$, respectively. The empirical power curves for the correlation structures in Set 1 and Set 2 are depicted in Figures 2 and 3, respectively.

Figure 2: Empirical power curves of F_B for Set 1

Figure 3: Empirical power curves of F_B for Set 2

The empirical power of the approximate F -test for the treatment effect is influenced by several factors, as demonstrated by the power curves in Figures 2 and 3. The explanations below assume that the simulation parameters not explicitly mentioned are held constant.

The power of the test increases with larger values of δ . This is because larger treatment effects lead to a greater deviation from the null hypothesis, making it more likely to reject the hypothesis that all treatment effects are zero. Increasing the number of sets within blocks generally increases the power. This is because more sets (i.e., more replications) provide a better estimate of the block-level treatment effect, which can improve the sensitivity of the test. Power also tends to increase with cluster level set size. This is because a larger set size yields a larger number of positively correlated error terms, which facilitates a reduction in the expected mean squared cluster error, making it easier to detect significant differences. Power decreases as the intraclass correlation increases. A high ICC signifies that, compared to cluster units, within-cluster units are more similar to each other. Thus, a large portion of experimental variability originates from differences among cluster units, which results in a higher mean squared cluster error. In turn, this yields a smaller statistical power.

Ranking quality is another factor that influences the empirical power. Power increases as cluster level ranking quality (ρ_1) improves. Larger values of ρ_1 indicate a stronger correlation structure. This leads to a meaningful separation among ranking groups of cluster units. Hence, when ρ_1 is larger, units within each ranking group are more homogeneous,

which ultimately yields a smaller expected mean squared cluster error. A similar effect is observed for large values of ρ_2 . In particular, larger values of ρ_2 signify a stronger separation among subsampling level ranking groups, which results in a smaller mean squared error.

The impact of ρ_1 and ρ_2 on the empirical power depends on the value of ICC . For example, better ranking quality at the subsampling level more significantly enhances empirical power when ICC is small. This is clear from Figure 2: the power curves in the first row ($ICC = 0.01$) are more separated than the power curves in the second row ($ICC = 0.5$). On the contrary, better ranking quality at the cluster level has more of an impact on empirical power when ICC is larger. In particular, the power curves in row 2 ($ICC = 0.5$) of Figure 3 are more separated from each other than the power curves in row 1 ($ICC = 0.01$).

We now compare the power curves for the correlation structures in Set 1 and Set 2. The power curves in row 1 of Figure 2 are more dispersed than the corresponding power curves in Figure 3. This implies that, for a smaller ICC , an efficient design at the subsampling level is more important than an efficient design at the cluster level, in terms of improving empirical power. The opposite holds for a larger ICC . In particular, the power curves in row 2 of Figure 2 are much closer together than the corresponding power curves in Figure 3. This suggests that, for a larger ICC , an efficient design at the cluster level is more important than an efficient design at the subsampling level, in terms of improving empirical power.

3.1 Assessing Ranking Quality

The efficiency of an ORCRBD depends on the ranking quality in stage 1 and 2 sampling. These ranking qualities may not be known a priori. However, the data can be used to estimate these ranking qualities. The EMS expressions in Table 5 suggest the following F -statistic for the cluster level ranking group effect:

$$F_C = \frac{MSC}{MSE}.$$

A large value of F_C implies that ranking cluster units accounts for a large portion of the total variation in the experiment. Hence, F_C can be used as a measure of the effectiveness of ranking.

An alternative method for assessing cluster level ranking quality involves estimating the parameter, ρ_1 . In estimating ρ_1 , we first define $\eta_1 = \rho_1\gamma$. We estimate this quantity using

$$\hat{\eta}_1 = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k \bar{Y}_{.k\dots}}{\sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}. \quad (9)$$

We then define θ_1^2 , the variance component of the cluster effect in model (8), as

$$\theta_1^2 = \gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2 \right).$$

When this equation is solved for γ and the unknown parameters are replaced with their corresponding estimators, we obtain the following:

$$\hat{\gamma} = \sqrt{\hat{\theta}_1^2 + \frac{(\hat{\eta}_1)^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}, \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{\theta}_1^2$ is the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) estimator of θ_1^2 obtained by fitting model (8) using the *lmer* function in R.

Since $\eta_1 = \rho_1\gamma$, we define

$$\hat{\rho}_1 = \frac{\hat{\eta}_1}{\hat{\gamma}},$$

where $\hat{\eta}_1$ and $\hat{\gamma}$ are expressed in equations (9) and (10), respectively. However, since the estimator of ρ_1 can yield impractical estimates (i.e., estimates bigger than 1), we use the following truncated estimator:

$$\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc} = \begin{cases} \hat{\rho}_1, & \hat{\rho}_1 \leq 1 \\ 1, & \hat{\rho}_1 > 1 \end{cases}.$$

A value of $\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc}$ close to 1 indicates that cluster level ranking group is an effective blocking factor, in terms of reducing experimental variation. A value of $\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc}$ close to 0 suggests that cluster level ranking group may not be a very effective blocking factor.

In a similar fashion, we assess the subsampling level ranking quality using the F -statistic,

$$F_S = \frac{MSS}{MSE},$$

where large values of F_S indicate a high quality of ranking at the subsampling level.

Arguments similar to those used in the estimation of ρ_1 yield an estimator for ρ_2 :

$$\hat{\rho}_{2,trunc} = \begin{cases} \hat{\rho}_2, & \hat{\rho}_2 \leq 1 \\ 1, & \hat{\rho}_2 > 1 \end{cases},$$

where

$$\hat{\rho}_2 = \frac{\hat{\eta}_2}{\hat{\sigma}}.$$

In this equation, $\hat{\eta}_2$ and $\hat{\sigma}$ are defined analogously to their cluster level counterparts, $\hat{\eta}_1$ and $\hat{\gamma}$, respectively. The estimator $\hat{\rho}_{2,trunc}$ has an analogous interpretation to that of $\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc}$.

Finally, we note that the estimators of τ , γ , and ρ_1 are of the same form for models (6) and (8). In particular, $\hat{\tau}$ is found by fitting the appropriate model in R with the *lmer* function. However, model (6) assumes simple random sampling is used in stage 2, so there is no ρ_2 parameter to estimate in this case. Also, the REML estimator of σ , $\hat{\sigma}$, is now found directly by fitting model (6) in R with the *lmer* function.

4. Optimal Sample Size Allocation

The ORCRBD requires two-stage sampling. To maximize the overall information content of the experiment, we must determine the optimal sample size at each stage. The optimization process often involves minimizing the variance of an estimator (e.g., pairwise treatment contrast estimator) for a pre-specified budget. In this section, we assume RSS is performed at the subsampling level of the ORCRBD unless stated otherwise.

For an ORCRBD with $H_1 = 2$ or $H_1 = 3$, the variance of any general treatment contrast estimator is a function of the expected mean squared cluster error and can be written as

$$Var\left(\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} b_h \bar{Y}_{..h\dots}\right) = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} b_h^2}{H_1 m p} E(MSCE), \quad (11)$$

where $\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} b_h = 0$. Equation (11) also holds when SRS is used at the subsampling level (with slight adjustments in notation). For an ORCRBD with $H_1 \geq 4$, the variance

of a pairwise treatment contrast estimator depends on the Latin square structure of the ORCRBD.

For a given H_1 , there are $\binom{H_1}{2}$ pairwise treatment contrast estimators. The average of the variances of these estimators can be expressed as

$$V_{avg} := \frac{1}{\binom{H_1}{2}} \sum_{h' < h=1}^{H_1} Var(\bar{Y}_{..h\dots} - \bar{Y}_{..h'\dots}) = \frac{2}{H_1 m p} E(MSCE). \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) also holds when SRS is used at the subsampling level (with slight adjustments in notation). This equation can be rewritten in terms of $ICC = \gamma^2 / (\sigma^2 + \gamma^2)$:

$$V_{avg} = \frac{2\sigma^2}{H_1 m p} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}{H_2} \right) + p \left(\frac{ICC}{1 - ICC} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2 \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}{H_1 - 1} \right) \right\}.$$

When $H_1 = 2$ or $H_1 = 3$, V_{avg} is exactly equal to the variance of any pairwise treatment contrast estimator. Hence, for these values of H_1 , minimizing V_{avg} is equivalent to minimizing the variance of any individual pairwise treatment contrast estimator. When $H_1 \geq 4$, minimizing V_{avg} subject to a cost constraint might not yield the m and p values that would result from minimizing the variance of an individual pairwise treatment contrast estimator under the same cost restriction. However, since V_{avg} depends on the variance of each pairwise treatment contrast estimator, we anticipate that the minimization of V_{avg} will yield sample sizes that approximate the true optimized m and p rather closely.

We use the following cost model to derive optimal sample sizes for stage 1 and 2 sampling:

$$T = H_1^2 m (C_1 + p C_2).$$

In this equation, T is the total budget (in dollars) of the experiment, $H_1^2 m$ is the total number of cluster units in the design, C_1 is the cost of sampling for any one cluster unit, and C_2 is the cost of sampling for any one subject within a cluster unit. We note that C_1 and C_2 include the per unit costs associated with ranking at the cluster level and subsampling level, respectively.

The optimal values of p and m are given by

$$p_{opt} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{C_1}{C_2} \right) \left(\frac{1 - ICC}{ICC} \right) \left(\frac{1 - \frac{\rho_2^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}{H_2}}{1 - \frac{\rho_1^2 \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}{H_1 - 1}} \right)}, \quad m_{opt} = \frac{T}{H_1^2 (C_1 + p_{opt} C_2)}. \quad (13)$$

For the ORCRBD with SRS at the subsampling level, the expressions for p_{opt} and m_{opt} follow by substituting $\rho_2 = 0$.

The formulas for the optimal p and m are intuitively revealing. Holding T , ICC , ρ_1 , ρ_2 , H_1 , and H_2 fixed, a cluster unit sampling cost that exceeds the within-cluster unit sampling cost yields a larger value of p_{opt} and smaller value of m_{opt} , as compared to when the cluster and subsampling level sampling costs both equal the lesser of the aforementioned costs. When T , C_1 , C_2 , ICC , ρ_1 , H_1 , and H_2 are fixed, increasing ρ_2 decreases p_{opt} , which forces m_{opt} to increase. The same thing happens if, holding all other quantities constant, ρ_2 is fixed and H_2 is increased. Thus, for fixed values of the other quantities, an effective blocking strategy at the subsampling level (i.e., a larger ρ_2 and/or H_2) leads to a smaller value of p_{opt} and larger value of m_{opt} . On the contrary, at the cluster level, with all other factors held constant, a pronounced separation among ranking groups (resulting from a larger ρ_1 and/or H_1) results in a larger value of p_{opt} and smaller value of m_{opt} . Finally, holding all other quantities constant, a smaller ICC leads to an increased value of p_{opt} and decreased value of m_{opt} , as compared to a larger ICC .

5. Estimation of Contrast Parameters

In this section, we consider developing inference for a treatment contrast parameter, Δ , defined as $\Delta = \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} b_h \beta_h$ with $\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} b_h = 0$. To simplify the notation, we can write models (6) and (8) in matrix form with the design matrix \mathbf{Z} :

$$\mathbf{Y}_N = \mathbf{Z}_N \boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_N = \boldsymbol{\mu}_N + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_N, \quad (14)$$

where $N = H_1^2 mp$, \mathbf{Z}_N is the design matrix for fixed effects, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the fixed effects parameter vector, and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_N$ is the error vector. For model (6), $\boldsymbol{\mu}_N$ can be written as $\boldsymbol{\mu}_N = (\mu_{ikhrt} = \mu + \alpha_i + \rho_1 \gamma \phi_k + \beta_h)$. For model (8), $\boldsymbol{\mu}_N$ takes the form $\boldsymbol{\mu}_N = (\mu_{ikhvrs} = \mu + \alpha_i + \rho_1 \gamma \phi_k + \beta_h + \rho_2 \sigma \omega_v)$. Let \mathbf{Q}_N be the subspace spanned by \mathbf{Z}_N . We define the projection matrix onto \mathbf{Q}_N as

$$\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Q}_N} = \mathbf{Z}_N (\mathbf{Z}_N^T \mathbf{Z}_N)^{-1} \mathbf{Z}_N^T.$$

Using the projection matrix, we estimate $\boldsymbol{\mu}_N$ with $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_N = \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Q}_N} \mathbf{Y}_N$. Let \mathbf{Q}_N^* be the subspace corresponding to the model without the treatment effect. Let $\mathbf{W}_N = \mathbf{Q}_N | \mathbf{Q}_N^* = \{\mathbf{q}_N \in \mathbf{Q}_N : \mathbf{q}_N \perp \mathbf{Q}_N^*\}$. This is the subspace corresponding to the treatment effect in model (14). Let

$$\mathbf{c}_N = \begin{cases} (c_{ikhrt} = \frac{b_h}{H_1 mp}), & \text{for model (6)} \\ (c_{ikhvrs} = \frac{b_h}{H_1 mp}), & \text{for model (8)} \end{cases},$$

where $\mathbf{b}^T = (b_1, \dots, b_{H_1})$ is the vector of contrast coefficients with $\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} b_h = 0$. We note that $\mathbf{c}_N \in \mathbf{W}_N$.

Theorem 1. *Let $\mathbf{c}_N \in \mathbf{W}_N$ be the vector of contrast coefficients for a treatment contrast parameter $\Delta = \mathbf{c}_N^T \boldsymbol{\mu}_N$. Assume H_1 is fixed. Then for any p , as $m \rightarrow \infty$, we have*

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\hat{\Delta}}^2}} (\hat{\Delta} - \Delta) \xrightarrow{d} N(0, 1),$$

where $\hat{\Delta} = \mathbf{c}_N^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_N = \mathbf{c}_N^T \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Q}_N} \mathbf{Y}_N$, $\sigma_{\hat{\Delta}}^2 = \text{Var}(\hat{\Delta}) = \mathbf{c}_N^T \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{W}_N} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{W}_N} \mathbf{c}_N$, and $\mathbf{V} = \text{Var}(\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_N)$.

For any general treatment contrast estimator, $\hat{\Delta}$, we can estimate $\sigma_{\hat{\Delta}}^2$ by $\widehat{\sigma}_{\hat{\Delta}}^2$, where

$$\widehat{\sigma}_{\hat{\Delta}}^2 = \widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\Delta}) = \mathbf{c}_N^T \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{W}_N} \widehat{\mathbf{V}} \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{W}_N} \mathbf{c}_N. \quad (15)$$

Since $\mathbf{W}_N \subset \mathbf{Q}_N$, $\widehat{\sigma}_{\hat{\Delta}}^2$ can equivalently be computed by replacing $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{W}_N}$ with $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Q}_N}$ in equation (15). In this equation, $\widehat{\mathbf{V}}$ is the variance matrix, \mathbf{V} , with parameters $\rho_1, \rho_2, \tau, \gamma$, and σ replaced by the corresponding estimates from Section 3.1.

However, for $H_1 \leq 3$, the variance of any general treatment contrast estimator can be expressed as a function of the expected mean squared cluster error:

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\Delta}) = \frac{\|\mathbf{b}\|^2}{H_1 mp} E(MSCE).$$

This quantity is estimated by

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}(\hat{\Delta}) = \frac{\|\mathbf{b}\|^2}{H_1 mp} MSCE. \quad (16)$$

An approximate $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ confidence interval for Δ is then given by

$$\hat{\Delta} \pm t_{df_{CE}, \alpha/2} \sqrt{\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})}. \quad (17)$$

In this formula, $df_{CE} = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$ is the degrees of freedom for the cluster error and $t_{df_{CE}, \alpha/2}$ is the upper $(\alpha/2)^{th}$ quantile of the Student's t -distribution with df_{CE} degrees of freedom.

We investigated the finite sample properties of $\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})$ in a simulation study of size 5,000 under models (6) and (8). The results for both models are similar, so we limit our discussion to model (8). The data were generated assuming the overall mean $\mu = 0$, no treatment effect, and no block effect. We used $\rho_1 = 0.5, 0.75, 1$; $\rho_2 = 0.75, 1$; $H_1 = 2, 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10, 50$; $H_2 = 3$; $d_2 = 2$; $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.1, 0.2, 0.5$. The ICC values were obtained using the following choices of (γ, σ) : (10, 30), (5, 10), and (1, 1), respectively.

We simulated the actual variance of $\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta}$ for various treatment contrast estimators as follows: for each of the 5,000 runs, we computed $\hat{\Delta}$ and then determined the variance of the 5,000 values of $\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta}$. This simulated actual variance is denoted as $Var_R(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta})$.

Next, we simulated the value of $\widehat{Var}(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta})$ for the same treatment contrast estimators by computing the average of 5,000 values of $\widehat{Var}(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta})$. Each of these values was obtained by fitting the model and computing $H_1 m p \widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})$. This simulated variance estimate is denoted as $\widehat{Var}_R(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta})$.

We assessed the accuracy of $\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})$ in estimating $Var(\hat{\Delta})$ using percent bias ($PBIAS$):

$$PBIAS = \left[\frac{\widehat{Var}_R(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta}) - Var_R(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta})}{Var_R(\sqrt{H_1 m p} \hat{\Delta})} \right] 100\%.$$

Small values of $PBIAS$ indicate that $\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})$ is an accurate estimator of $Var(\hat{\Delta})$. Positive and negative $PBIAS$ values imply an overestimation and underestimation, respectively, of the true variance.

In Table 7, we provide percent biases for three specific contrast estimators: $\hat{\Delta}_{12} = \bar{Y}_{..2...} - \bar{Y}_{..1...}$, $\hat{\Delta}_{123} = \bar{Y}_{..1...} - 2\bar{Y}_{..2...} + \bar{Y}_{..3...}$, and $\hat{\Delta}_{1234} = \bar{Y}_{..4...} - \bar{Y}_{..3...} + \bar{Y}_{..2...} - \bar{Y}_{..1...}$. We only report results for $H_1 = 3, 4$, since simulation results for $H_1 = 2$ and $H_1 = 3$ are similar.

When $H_1 = 3$, the percent bias values do not exhibit a consistent departure from zero in one direction. There is a mix of positive and negative values, and these values are reasonably close to zero. A similar pattern is observed for $H_1 = 4$ and $\rho_1 \neq 1$. However, when $H_1 = 4$ and $\rho_1 = 1$, the percent bias values are generally positive, displaying a relatively larger magnitude than when $H_1 = 3$ and $\rho_1 = 1$. When $H_1 = 4$, we note that the impact of $\rho_1 = 1$ on the magnitude of the percent bias is more pronounced than when ρ_2 is set to 1.

Inspection of Table 7 also reveals that the percent bias depends on the true value of ρ_1 and the cluster level set size, H_1 . When $H_1 = 3$, expression (16) emerges as a remarkably accurate estimator of $Var(\hat{\Delta})$, yielding minimal percent bias even in cases of small m . Similar commendable results are observed for expression (15), which serves as an accurate estimator for $Var(\hat{\Delta})$ when H_1 is set to 4 and ρ_1 is not equal to 1.

Notably, for each contrast estimator and ICC value in Table 7(b), the magnitude of $PBIAS$ when $\rho_1 = 1$ and m is small ($m \leq 5$) is larger than it is for all other combinations of ρ_1 and m , provided ρ_2 is fixed. This observation is anticipated. Since $\rho_1 = 1$ lies at the boundary of the parameter space, estimates of this parameter can exceed 1. However,

through truncation, REML estimation ensures that the estimate of ρ_1 remains within the parameter space. Although this leads to biased outcomes, the bias of $\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})$ is minimal when m is large ($m \geq 10$).

Table 7: Percent biases under model (8) for various ρ_1 , m , and ρ_2 values when $ICC = 0.1, 0.2, 0.5$; $H_2 = 3$; and $d_2 = 2$

(a) $H_1 = 3$									(b) $H_1 = 4$								
ρ_1	m	ρ_2	$ICC = 0.1$		$ICC = 0.2$		$ICC = 0.5$		ρ_1	m	ρ_2	$ICC = 0.1$		$ICC = 0.2$		$ICC = 0.5$	
			$\hat{\Delta}_{12}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{123}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{12}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{123}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{12}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{123}$				$\hat{\Delta}_{12}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{1234}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{12}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{1234}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{12}$	$\hat{\Delta}_{1234}$
0.50	3	0.75	2.36	3.40	1.65	2.87	0.43	1.76	0.50	3	0.75	-2.78	-3.31	-1.05	-2.38	0.40	-2.22
0.50	5	0.75	1.38	2.87	2.02	3.05	2.59	3.00	0.50	5	0.75	-5.14	-5.60	-3.39	-3.91	-2.47	-2.67
0.50	10	0.75	0.73	-2.06	0.37	-2.08	-0.16	-1.69	0.50	10	0.75	1.37	2.93	2.13	4.18	2.66	4.33
0.50	50	0.75	-1.46	-0.98	-1.27	-1.14	-0.82	-0.83	0.50	50	0.75	3.14	0.78	2.57	1.07	1.25	1.05
0.75	3	0.75	2.03	1.19	1.76	0.99	0.68	0.61	0.75	3	0.75	-0.72	-3.75	-0.35	-3.49	-0.01	-2.47
0.75	5	0.75	-2.83	-2.31	-3.12	-2.35	-3.26	-2.03	0.75	5	0.75	0.61	1.35	0.93	1.01	0.64	-0.08
0.75	10	0.75	0.19	-1.63	0.41	-0.92	0.60	0.39	0.75	10	0.75	0.68	-0.85	0.09	-0.88	-0.83	-1.70
0.75	50	0.75	0.28	2.57	0.69	1.89	1.25	0.37	0.75	50	0.75	3.79	2.13	3.42	1.63	2.46	0.72
1	3	0.75	2.40	1.45	2.37	1.85	2.09	2.51	1	3	0.75	5.50	6.18	7.00	6.76	8.96	7.29
1	5	0.75	-1.07	-2.17	-0.40	-1.84	1.27	-0.48	1	5	0.75	6.54	6.23	7.47	7.43	8.73	9.20
1	10	0.75	0.52	3.10	0.58	3.83	0.95	4.57	1	10	0.75	0.12	-0.68	0.88	-0.03	3.60	2.68
1	50	0.75	-0.53	0.57	-0.05	1.09	0.57	1.98	1	50	0.75	0.44	3.81	0.83	4.04	1.83	4.55
0.50	3	1	0.37	-1.36	0.96	-0.94	1.72	-0.15	0.50	3	1	-2.19	-2.36	-1.28	-1.43	-1.34	-1.49
0.50	5	1	3.52	4.58	2.90	4.40	1.52	3.61	0.50	5	1	-0.17	-0.50	-0.0003	-0.16	-1.12	-1.14
0.50	10	1	-0.90	-0.54	-1.26	-0.57	-1.57	-0.71	0.50	10	1	-0.56	-1.35	-0.17	1.91	-0.22	1.67
0.50	50	1	0.42	-0.11	0.04	-0.38	-0.24	-0.63	0.50	50	1	0.49	1.15	0.80	1.30	0.99	1.56
0.75	3	1	0.17	0.17	-0.46	-0.60	-0.94	-1.24	0.75	3	1	-0.93	-0.90	-0.67	-0.51	-0.42	-0.02
0.75	5	1	0.06	1.48	-0.27	1.25	0.29	1.53	0.75	5	1	1.07	1.78	0.12	2.09	-1.19	2.05
0.75	10	1	-2.09	-0.70	-2.40	-1.29	-2.68	-2.13	0.75	10	1	-1.79	-0.42	-1.80	-0.95	-1.85	-1.56
0.75	50	1	-2.57	-1.98	-3.12	-1.82	-3.00	-1.03	0.75	50	1	2.60	1.65	2.86	1.50	2.79	1.50
1	3	1	2.42	3.97	3.06	3.77	3.88	3.24	1	3	1	9.71	12.93	9.75	13.88	9.43	15.45
1	5	1	-0.24	-0.54	-0.69	-0.76	-1.64	-1.28	1	5	1	10.17	10.53	10.97	12.46	11.72	15.11
1	10	1	0.42	1.03	0.91	1.35	1.83	1.71	1	10	1	7.25	6.95	6.78	6.86	6.31	7.39
1	50	1	1.48	2.83	1.73	3.37	2.12	3.75	1	50	1	1.75	1.16	1.80	1.20	1.91	1.82

In another simulation study, we examined the coverage probabilities of confidence intervals for the parameter, $\Delta_{12} = \beta_2 - \beta_1$. The observed coverage probabilities closely align with the nominal coverage probability of 0.95.

5.1 Multiple Comparison Methods

In this section, we construct Bonferroni, Tukey, and Scheffé multiple comparison procedures. For the Bonferroni method, approximate $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ simultaneous confidence intervals are calculated using the following formula:

$$\hat{\Delta} \pm t_{df_{CE}, \alpha/(2n)} \sqrt{\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta})},$$

where n is the number of comparisons of interest, $df_{CE} = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$ is the degrees of freedom for the cluster error, and $t_{df_{CE}, \alpha/(2n)}$ is the upper $\alpha/(2n)^{th}$ quantile of the Student's t -distribution with df_{CE} degrees of freedom. The variance of $\hat{\Delta}$ is estimated using equation (16) when $H_1 \leq 3$ and equation (15) when $H_1 > 3$.

For the Tukey procedure, the simultaneous confidence intervals for $\Delta_{h'h} = \beta_h - \beta_{h'}$ are calculated as follows:

$$\hat{\Delta}_{h'h} \pm \frac{q_{H_1, df_{CE}, \alpha}}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\widehat{Var}(\hat{\Delta}_{h'h})},$$

where $q_{H_1, df_{CE}, \alpha}$ is the upper α^{th} quantile of the studentized range distribution with H_1 groups (treatments) and degrees of freedom, df_{CE} . The variance of $\hat{\Delta}_{h'h}$ is estimated using equation (16) when $H_1 \leq 3$ and equation (15) when $H_1 > 3$.

For the Scheffé procedure, the set of approximate $100(1-\alpha)\%$ simultaneous confidence intervals for the treatment contrasts of interest is obtained using the following formula:

$$\hat{\Delta} \pm [(H_1 - 1)F_{H_1-1, df_{CE}, \alpha}]^{1/2} \sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{b}\|^2}{H_1 m p} MSC E},$$

where \mathbf{b} is the H_1 -dimensional vector containing the coefficients for the contrast of interest, $MSC E$ is the mean squared cluster error, and $F_{H_1-1, df_{CE}, \alpha}$ is the upper α^{th} quantile of the central F -distribution with numerator and denominator degrees of freedom $H_1 - 1$ and df_{CE} , respectively.

We performed a simulation study of size 5,000 under model (8) to investigate the performance of the Bonferroni, Tukey, and Scheffé multiple comparison methods. The data in this simulation study were generated assuming the overall mean $\mu = 0$, no treatment effect, and no block effect. We let $\rho_1 = 0.5, 0.75, 1$; $\rho_2 = 0.5, 0.75, 1$; $H_1 = 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10, 50$; $H_2 = 3$; $d_2 = 2$; $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.1, 0.5$. The ICC values were obtained using (γ, σ) values equal to $(10, 30)$ and $(1, 1)$, respectively. We did a simulation study under model (6) as well, but results were similar and, therefore, omitted.

For each set of simulation parameters, we computed simultaneous 95% confidence intervals for the pairwise treatment contrasts, $\Delta_{h'h} = \beta_h - \beta_{h'}$ ($h' < h$). The coverage probability was then calculated as the proportion of times that all of the confidence intervals contained their corresponding $\Delta_{h'h}$ value.

To compare these coverage probabilities, we present side-by-side boxplots in Figure 4. For every combination of ICC and H_1 , all Bonferroni and Scheffé coverage probabilities exceed 0.95; however, the Bonferroni approach tends to produce coverage probabilities closer to 0.95 than the Scheffé approach. The Tukey procedure tends to produce coverage probabilities closer to 0.95 than both the Bonferroni and Scheffé approaches.

For a fixed H_1 , coverage probabilities are similar for $ICC = 0.1, 0.5$. Note that, for a normal linear model with independent and identically distributed error variances, the Tukey procedure yields a simultaneous confidence level exactly equal to $100(1 - \alpha)\%$ (provided the experiment is balanced). In our ORCRBD, when $H_1 = 3$, the Tukey procedure yields coverage probabilities very close to 0.95, regardless of ICC . However, when $H_1 = 4$, some coverage probabilities for the Tukey confidence intervals are slightly inflated; nonetheless, most of the coverage probabilities are still close to 0.95. The inflated values primarily occur when $\rho_1 = 1$, likely due to the truncation involved in the REML estimation approach.

6. Educational Application of the ORCRBD

In this section, we utilize the ORCRBD to analyze data from the High School Longitudinal Study of 2009 (HSLs:09), a comprehensive study following over 23,000 ninth graders from 944 schools across the United States. This study aims to track student trajectories from high school into college, the workforce, and beyond.

The HSLs:09 design includes the selection of both schools and students within schools, with extensive student-level data collected, including demographic information (e.g., sex, race) and academic performance (e.g., test scores). For more detailed information on HSLs:09, readers are encouraged to visit <https://nces.ed.gov/surveys/hsls09/>.

As part of the HSLs:09, students took a math exam in the fall of ninth grade (2009) and again in the spring of eleventh grade (2012). The variable X1TXMSCR represents the math score in 2009 and is an estimate of the number of correct responses a student would have achieved if they had answered all 72 questions in the pool. The variable X2TXMTH represents the 2012 mathematics theta score.

Figure 4: Performance of Multiple Comparison Procedures for an ORCRBD with RSS at subsampling level

In our ORCRBD analysis, we use X1TXMSCR as the ranking variable and X2TXMTH as the response variable. Additionally, we incorporate X1REGION—the region of the United States where a student’s base year school is located—as the blocking variable. X1REGION has four levels: “Northeast,” “Midwest,” “South,” and “West.”

We will assess the empirical power of the ORCRBD by comparing it to a traditional cluster randomized block design (CRBD) that also utilizes X1REGION as a blocking variable. Our analysis begins with the use of pre-processed data by Wang et al. (2016). This data set has been refined to exclude schools with fewer than 20 sampled students, resulting in information for 12,533 students across 472 schools. However, this data set contains some discrepancies. For instance, 34 schools are classified as being in multiple geographic regions. To address this, we have removed these schools from the analysis, focusing on the remaining 438 schools and 10,929 students as our population.

In this population, the cluster level ranking quality is characterized by the correlation, ρ_1 , between X1TXMSCR and X2TXMTH at the cluster level. To calculate this, we first determine the X1TXMSCR (ranking variable) and X2TXMTH (response variable) averages for each of the 438 schools. We then compute the correlation coefficient between these averages, resulting in $\rho_1 = 0.9052$.

The subsampling level ranking quality is defined by the correlation, ρ_2 , between X1TXMSCR and X2TXMTH at the subsampling level. To calculate ρ_2 , we compute the correlation between the X1TXMSCR and X2TXMTH values corresponding to the 10,929

students, yielding $\rho_2 = 0.7754$.

The between-cluster variance, γ^2 , and within-cluster variance, σ^2 , are determined by computing the variance components from a one-way random effect ANOVA model, where school ID is considered the factor of interest. This analysis yields $\gamma^2 = 0.2960$ and $\sigma^2 = 1.0078$. Finally, the *ICC* is calculated as $ICC = \gamma^2 / (\gamma^2 + \sigma^2) = 0.2270$.

Using the modified population, we conducted a simulation study of size 10,000 to examine the empirical power of the ORCRBD and CRBD. Given that the blocking variable (X1REGION) has four levels, the ORCRBDs in this study were configured with four cluster level ranking groups and four treatment levels ($H_1 = 4$). In the ORCRBDs, the ranks of cluster units were determined based on school X1TXMSCR averages, while the ranks of students within schools were determined by individual X1TXMSCR scores.

The efficiency of the ORCRBD depends on two sample sizes, p and m . Optimal values of p and m can be found using equation (13) and depend on factors such as sampling cost of a cluster unit (C_1) and within-cluster unit (C_2). The unit costs C_1 and C_2 include any expenses associated with cluster level and subsampling level ranking processes, respectively. For this simulation study, we fixed the sampling costs (C_1, C_2) as (0.25, 0.75), (0.5, 0.5), (0.75, 0.25), and (0.9, 0.1). Additionally, for each (C_1, C_2) combination, we set the subsampling level set size to be $H_2 = 2, 3, 4$. The total budget for the experiment was set at $T = \$100$. For each combination of (C_1, C_2) and H_2 , we calculated an optimal subsampling cycle size (d_2), optimal number of within-cluster units (p), and optimal number of within-block sets (m). For a fair comparison, the sample sizes were matched in the ORCRBDs and CRBDs. Sampling with replacement was used at both the cluster and subsampling level in each design.

For each combination of simulation parameters in the ORCRBD and CRBD, we computed the empirical power under the directional alternative hypotheses,

$$H_a : \left\{ \beta_1 = -\frac{\Delta}{2}, \beta_2 = 0, \beta_3 = 0, \beta_4 = \frac{\Delta}{2} \right\},$$

where $\Delta = \delta \sqrt{\gamma^2 + \sigma^2}$ and $\delta = 0(0.2)2$. For the ORCRBD, the empirical power was computed as the proportion of $F_B = MSB/MSC E$ values greater than the 95th percentile of a F_{df_1, df_2} distribution, where $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$. The empirical power of the CRBD was computed in the same manner as for the ORCRBD, with the numerator and denominator degrees of freedom on the central F -distribution replaced by the expressions $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = H_1^2 m - 2H_1 + 1$.

The empirical power curves for this simulation study are depicted in Figure 5. In each of the four panels, the black curves represent the ORCRBD, and the blue curves represent the CRBD. Additionally, within each panel, ORCRBD and CRBD curves of the same line type indicate matched sample sizes.

When $\delta = 0$ (i.e., no shift), the test of the treatment effect for both the ORCRBD and CRBD yields Type I error rates that are reasonably close to the nominal value of 0.05. Specifically, the ORCRBD Type I error rates range from 0.055 to 0.064, while the CRBD Type I error rates range from 0.044 to 0.054. The slight inflation of Type I error rates for the ORCRBD may be attributed to ranking errors at the cluster and subsampling level.

When $\delta > 0$, the empirical power of the approximate F -test corresponding to the ORCRBD generally exceeds the empirical power of the F -test corresponding to the CRBD. For instance, when $\delta = 0.8$, the ORCRBD with $C_1 = 0.75$, $C_2 = 0.25$, $m = 3$, $H_2 = 4$, and $d_2 = 2$ achieves an empirical power of 0.976, while the corresponding CRBD achieves an empirical power of 0.786.

Figure 5: Empirical power curves for various ORCRBDs and CRBDs with $H_1 = 4$ blocks, $H_1 m = 4m$ schools in each block, and p students sampled from each school

7. Concluding Remarks

Traditional cluster randomized designs, while often more practical than completely randomized designs, are typically less efficient. To address this limitation, we propose the order restricted cluster randomized block design (ORCRBD). The ORCRBD is a novel two-stage design that incorporates order restricted randomization (ORR) at the cluster level and either ranked set sampling (RSS) or simple random sampling (SRS) at the subsampling level. ORR and RSS aim to reduce between-cluster and within-cluster variability, respectively, leading to a design that is more efficient than existing cluster randomized designs in the literature.

We proposed linear models for the ORCRBD that incorporate ranking in both stage 1 and stage 2 sampling, along with other sources of variation (e.g., block and treatment effects). Using these models, we derived expressions for the expected mean squares (EMS) and utilized them to develop an approximate F -test for the treatment effect.

We acknowledge that planning an ORCRBD is more intricate than planning a completely randomized design, given the need to consider two sample sizes. Consequently, we derived optimal cluster and within-cluster sample sizes for a given cost model. The optimal sample sizes depend on factors like sampling costs, intracluster correlation coefficient

(*ICC*), set sizes, and ranking qualities. For instance, a smaller *ICC* corresponds to a larger optimal number of within-cluster units and a smaller optimal number of cluster units in a cell, as compared to a larger *ICC*.

Under the ORCRBD, general treatment contrast estimators follow a limiting normal distribution. We developed approximate confidence intervals for treatment contrasts, including adjustments for multiple comparisons.

The ORCRBD is applicable across a wide range of fields, including public health, medicine, and education. We demonstrated the utility of the ORCRBD by applying it to the High School Longitudinal Study of 2009, an ongoing educational study tracking students since their freshman year of high school. Through a simulation study, we demonstrated that the ORCRBD is more powerful than a traditional cluster randomized block design.

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